

1. Provisional title. Reducing demographic bias in large language model loan underwriting: a registered report comparing rule-based mitigation strategies

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3. Field and keywords. Field: computer science; machine learning; fairness in artificial intelligence. Keywords: large language models; algorithmic fairness; credit underwriting; demographic bias; counterfactual fairness; constitutional AI; rule-based prompting; fair lending.

4. Research question(s). Prior work has shown that large language models (LLMs) recommend more loan denials for minority applicants than for applicants with the same background in every other way, and that a simple "be unbiased" instruction can reduce this gap. It's still unclear which types of guidance work best and why—or if these insights apply outside the context of race. This study asks: (RQ1) Do LLMs exhibit demographic bias in mortgage decisions across race/ethnicity, gender, and immigration status? (RQ2) Among prewritten rule documents — generic fairness principles, regulatory-principle texts, and structured decision rubrics — which ones work best to reduce that bias relative to no guidance and to an off-topic placebo? (RQ3) Do strict guardrails work better than simple guiding principles, and do they end up hurting the quality of the final decision? The study evaluates rule-based prompting as a deployable, retraining-free, regulator-auditable mitigation.

5. Hypotheses. H1: When left unguided, the baseline model shows measurable demographic bias on at least one protected attribute. This bias shows up in both the group approval-rate gap and the counterfactual flip rate. H2: fairness-relevant rule documents reduce bias relative to both baseline and an off-topic placebo. H3: Structuring the process—whether through a scoring rubric or a self-critique loop—reduces bias far more effectively than simply stating general principles. H4: mitigation conditions differ in their effect on decision quality, revealing a fairness–accuracy tradeoff.

6. Study design and methods. We use a counterfactual design where every variation is tested across every single item. Synthetic mortgage applications are generated with financial fields calibrated to public HMDA data and held identical across counterfactual variants of each application; only the protected-attribute signal varies, conveyed through three channels (name-based proxy, explicit demographic field, explicit immigration-status field). Synthetic data is used so that applications can be released in full without privacy restriction, and so financial profiles are exactly matched across counterfactual pairs. Each application is evaluated under seven conditions — C0 no-guidance baseline; C1 off-topic placebo document; C2 generic fairness principles; C3 regulatory-principle text; C4 structured scoring rubric; C5 self-critique loop; C6 rubric plus self-critique — crossed with at least two pinned LLM model snapshots, with multiple samples per cell at fixed temperature. A deterministic financial scoring function, defined over financial fields only, provides a ground-truth label for decision quality. Applications are stratified by ground-truth margin (clear-approve / borderline / clear-deny), with the borderline band oversampled. Sample size and samples per cell are fixed by a pre-IPA calibration pilot. Bias-control level: 6 — all main data generation and experimental runs occur after in-principle acceptance; only the calibration pilot precedes it.

7. Key analyses. Primary: mixed-effects logistic regression of the approval decision on protected-attribute × condition, with random intercepts for base application and model. Pre-specified contrasts on the counterfactual flip rate test each hypothesis — flip rate versus zero (H1); each fairness condition versus baseline and versus placebo (H2); process-constraining versus declarative conditions (H3). Claims that a method removes bias are supported only via two-one-sided-tests equivalence against a pre-registered smallest effect size of interest. Decision quality (agreement with the ground-truth label) and error-rate gaps are compared across conditions to characterise the fairness–accuracy tradeoff (H4). Holm correction is applied across the family of condition contrasts.

8. Conclusions that will be drawn given different results. This study extends prior findings (which manipulated only race and tested one or two prompt styles) to three protected attributes and a structured ladder of mitigation mechanisms, with a placebo control and pre-registered equivalence testing. If H1 holds, it confirms and broadens evidence of LLM underwriting bias to gender and immigration status; if bias appears for race but not other attributes, that itself delimits the phenomenon. If H2 holds, rule documents reduce bias beyond a generic long-text effect; if only the versus-baseline contrast holds but not versus-placebo, the apparent benefit is attributable to appending authoritative text rather than to fairness content — a cautionary finding absent from prior work. If H3 holds, constraining the decision process outperforms stating principles, guiding deployment toward rubric-style designs; if not, simple declarative guidance suffices, reinforcing prior results. H4 quantifies each method's cost: bias reduction achieved partly through degraded accuracy is a materially different outcome from bias reduction at no quality cost, a distinction prior studies did not isolate. Every outcome is informative and publishable, which is the rationale for the Registered Report format.

9. Key references. 1. Kleinberg et al. (2017), <https://doi.org/10.4230/LIPIcs.ITCS.2017.43>. 2. Kusner et al. (2017), <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1703.06856>. 3. Bai et al. (2022), <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2212.08073>. 4. Bowen et al. (2024), <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4812158>. 5. Cook & Kazinnik (2025), <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2506.17490>.